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THE EFFECT OF DIGITAL MEDIA ON JOB PERFORMANCE: A CASE STUDY OF TELECOMMUNICATION EMPLOYEES IN IHS TOWERS AND ZTE NIGERIA LIMITED

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Abstract: This study examined digital media and job performance of telecommunication employees of IHS Tower and ZTE Nigeria Limited in Lagos State, Nigeria. The objectives of the study were to find out the digital media tools that help telecommunication employees of IHS Tower and ZTE Nigeria Limited in their in job performance. The theoretical framework of the study was the adaptive structural theory and system theory. The research design adopted for this study was the descriptive survey design. The population of this study consisted of the IHS Tower and ZTE Nigeria Limited workers (staff) in Lagos state. According to the telecommunication companies Administrative Officers in 2023, the total population of IHS Tower is 600 and ZTE Nigeria Limited is 185. The total population is 785 (Seven hundred and eighty-five). To obtain the required sample size, Krejcie and Morgan Table was used to obtain the sample size of 254. The sampling method adopted was multi-stage sampling and data for this study obtained using copies of questionnaire. Data were analysed using the descriptive and inferential statistical analysis. Finding revealed that the digital media tools telecommunication employees of IHS Tower and ZTE Nigeria Limited engage in job performance were Google drive, browsers, servers, media hub, YouTube, Websites, portal sites, podcasts, blogs, webcast, Skype, dropbox, Evernote, HBO Go, Textplus, Picassa, Androi and Flipboard. The study concluded that digital media tools employed by telecommunication employees for job performance, ranged from collaborative platforms like Goggle Drive and servers to communication tools such as chatbots and file sharing platforms. Based on the finding, the study recommended that organizations should employ digital media tools such as Goggle drive, browsers, servers, media hubs, YouTube, websites, cloud storage, file sharing platforms, assistant gadgets, for improved job performance.

Keywords: Digital Media, Job Performance, Telecommunication, Employees

Introduction

Digital media are great in enabling employees to interact and share ideas that can build a sense of community and trust, encourage innovation, solve problems in real-time, and perform jobs credibly. Digital media are a great way to break down communication barriers to transfer the employee's job performance, experience and promote all innovation and growth. It would be in the best interest of organizations to focus on digital media within the

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organizations, which may bestow the organization with many benefits. Digital media are vital for both the organization and for its day-to-day existence. Digital media have the power to engage employees within the organization and allow the organization to ensure enhanced productivity. However, the question remains, how is management responsible for ensuring that communication occurs within the organization and how is the effectiveness of the communication evaluated appropriately? The more transparent an organization is, the more widely its internal information is shared. Digital media are vital aspects of how the job performance and relationships between the organization and its employees are evaluated, which means that open communication indicates a stronger relationship and better job performance. In today's lexicon, performance is an important variable in work organization and has become a significant indicator in measuring organizational performance in many studies. Employee performance can also be measured through the combination of expected behaviour and task-related aspects. In reality, a performance that is based on an absolute value or relative judgment may reflect overall organizational performance. However, performance measurement is based on the performance appraisal items that offer higher reliability in evaluating performance (Dessler, 2011). High-performance employees pursue a higher level of individual and organizational performance which involves quality, productivity, innovation rate, and cycle time of performance and therefore will be able to assist the organization to achieve its strategic aims and sustain the organization's competitive advantage (Dessler, 2011). Thus, to attract and sustain higher employee satisfaction and performance, the employer needs to treat their workers as the most important internal resources and gratify them because committed and satisfied employees are normally high performers that contribute towards organizational productivity.

Job performance has been identified as the significant key for organizations to gain competitive advantage and superior productivity. Although competitive advantage is more relevant to the private sector, it can be extended to the public sector by including 'serving the public' because it is the ultimate objective of the public sector. There is a huge need to communicate consistently and clearly to achieve employees' job performance. Digital media are considered crucial for achieving employees' good job performance. Communication between management and employees and reliable information sharing is critical in promoting a sense of commitment and belonging as well as helping employees to successfully understand the goals of the organization by performing better in his/her job. Employee job performance, relationships, and trust between employees are key results of successful digital media engagement.

A positive employee attitude can be formed early and within the confinement of the organization itself through the use of digital media. This provides evidence that there is a need for management to use effective digital media with their employees to become a trusted source of information for internal stakeholders. What this means is that effective digital media and employees' good job performance can endear the reputation of an organization, reduce management-employee conflicts and forestall the escalation of conflicts. In the current information age, the effectiveness of communication serves as a bridge that connects the employees, customers, prospects, and partners to the organization towards a mutual goal. Be it internal or external, communication is the life wire that boosts all aspects of an organization.

Communication helps in the setting and realization of the company's goal and objective; management of human and material resources and finally motivating, creating a condition for members to air their views and perform their jobs.

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Digital media also refer to as digital media, web-based media, or social media as the case may be, are the enviable trendy tools available in our world today. Through the Internet, the digital media world has strongly become part of our daily routines. Paving their way through social networking sites, these online platforms have redefined how consumers and businesses interact with each other. In the Western world, online media especially social media have been speculated to be a transforming drive among consumers' behaviour. This change has brought drastic changes and consequences for firms, products, and brands. Accordingly, consumers are increasingly spending their time online and using This digital or digital media. These media tool provides some advantages over the contemporary medium of organizational communication. Using digital media promotes active participation and engagement of all parties, especially the customers; help shapes business and organization marketing experience, provides the organization with information to adapt to the changing needs of consumers, and brings high and quality job performance.

The challenges of managing personal safety, family matters, and work-related duties do not seem to be simple. On the contrary, from day to day the workers face new challenges and problems, and how they tackle these challenges will have profound consequences on their productivity and company success. By connecting employees beyond the boundaries of their geographies, digital media empower employees to direct their performance from the bottom up. It allows them to build communities of interest, shares ideas, solve problem and collaborate in ways that make sense to them, and whole deliver measurable organization value. Digital media in a telecommunication company allows organization to communicate key information so that employees feel informed, motivated, and empowered. Digital media enable great employee performance which leads to brand advocacy, happy customer, successful business, and high satisfaction with service.

IHS Tower Nigeria Limited was founded in 2001, IHS Towers is one of the largest independent owners, operators, and developers of shared telecommunications infrastructure in the world. IHS is the largest independent tower operator in six of the nine markets in which it operates, and the only independent tower operator in five of these markets, with over 30,500 towers in its portfolio. IHS provides mission-critical telecommunications infrastructure to their customers, most of whom are leading multinational organizations, who in turn provide wireless voice and data services to their end users. In doing so, they help facilitate mobile communications coverage for approximately 600 million people (World Bank Data, 2021) across their footprint, supporting economies to implement nationwide digital agendas and IHS Towers has operations across Africa, Latin America, and the Middle East. IHS Towers provides a wide range of services across emerging markets (IHS Nigeria Limited, 2022). ZTE Corporation is a global leader in telecommunications and information technology. Founded in 1985 and listed on both the Hong Kong and Shenzhen Stock Exchanges, the company has been committed to providing innovative technologies and integrated solutions for global operators, government and enterprises, and consumers from over 160 countries across the globe. Serving over 1/4 of the global population, the company is dedicated to enabling connectivity and trust everywhere for a better future. ZTE has complete end-to-end product lines and integrated solutions in the telecommunications industry. Bolstered with its all series of wireless, services, devices, and professional telecommunications services, the company has great capability of flexibly satisfying the diversified requirements and pursuit for rapid innovations of global operators and government and enterprise network customers.

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The telecommunication industry in Nigeria has experienced rapid growth and transformation in recent years, primarily driven by advancement in technology. With the increasing demand for seamless communication, telecommunication companies have heavily relied on digital media platforms to connect their teams, particularly in geographically dispersed locations. Hence, this study is set to explore the correlation between the utilisation of digital media and job performance among telecommunication employees at IHS Tower and ZTE Nigeria Limited in Lagos State.

Statement of the problem

The IHS Tower Nigeria Limited and ZTE Nigeria Limited adopted working remotely, away from the traditional facilities to maintain a link to the office and employees. This involves telecommuting, working from home, teleworking, mobile work, flexi place, satellite office, detached units, distance meetings, or digital organizations. For telecommunication employee relations, it helps productivity, profitability and flexibility, and improvement in remote collaboration. Nevertheless, lack of cooperation and team spirit can decrease timeliness of work completion. There are challenges or hindrances related to the integration of digital media in the work environment of IHS Tower and ZTE Nigeria Limited such as inadequate or outdated technological infrastructure, security concerns, employee training and skill gaps, cultural resistance to change (resistance from employees accustomed to traditional modes of communication), network connectivity issues, over-reliance on digital platforms and cost implications which hinder the seamless integration of digital media, impacting communication and collaboration among telecommunication employees. These challenges are crucial for successfully integrating digital media in the work environment of telecommunication companies and optimising job performance.

The way digital media are diffused on job performance by telecommunication companies' employees needs to be known to harness more from employees in creating a working environment to satisfy the needs of employees as well as their performance. Employees are the major valuable assets of an organization in which without them, it is hard to realise its basic objectives. By investigating how telecommunication employees use digital media and their job performance will provide valuable insights into the dynamics of modern workplace communication. The understanding of the specific challenges and hindrances associated with the integration of digital media will enhance efficiency and effectiveness in these companies. Therefore, this study sets out to examine how the telecommunication employees of IHS Tower and ZTE Nigeria Limited in Lagos State need the digital media in job performance.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to assess the digital media and job performance by telecommunication employees of IHS Tower and ZTE Nigeria Limited in Lagos State, Nigeria. The objectives of the study were to:

1. identify the digital media tools that help telecommunication employees of IHS Tower and ZTE Nigeria Limited in their in job performance;
3. investigate how effective telecommunication employees of IHS Tower and ZTE Nigeria Limited's job performance using digital;

Literature Review

Digital Communication

Malhotra and Majchrzak (2015) view digital communication systems are those that use computers to structure and process information and use telecommunications networks to facilitate its exchange. These systems include e-mail, voice messaging, computer conferencing, etc. The rapid development of technologies that support

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communication and facilitate the exchange of data and information, including the internet, telephony, broadcast media, and all kinds of audio and video transmission technologies, improves the teamwork undertaken within geographically distributed project teams. Digital Communication is the key to getting things done in an organization and provides a vehicle enabling employees to make decisions, collaborate, and achieve results as established by the firm (Zbar, 2012). Digital communication technology allows employees to connect and this connectivity has also enabled employees to communicate in real-time wherever they are located across the globe, at minimal cost (Berry, 2011). And, as many firms have become global, how employees are communicating with one another and working together has inevitably changed.

Trace of Digital Communication

The advent of longer-distance (digital) communication started with the gradual development and invention of new technology after the invention of basic electrical signals. It was over a span of three centuries, a lot of communication technology such as telegraph (1792), Morse code (1835-1843), telephone (1876), cellular phones (1947), satellite communication (1963), Intranet communication (1969), ARPANET- brought in the age of communication that gradually infused speed increased the frontiers of communication into the entire communication environment (Hamid, 2020).

Most of the technology over the three centuries had limited use; within the highest circle of scientific research, government, and military divisions. It was out of reach for daily use in private businesses, let alone by the common man. However, the initial contribution of these technologies and the gradual expansion of their use and availability made it possible for the larger use of these technologies in the elite class of societies starting mid-19th century and later spread to other societal classes.

The advent of the Internet ushered in a new era in the area of communication technologies. By the mid-1990s the Internet has had a tremendous impact on culture and commerce, including the rise of near-instant communication by electronic mail, instant messaging, Voice over Internet Protocol (VoIP), two-way interactive video calls, and the World Wide Web with its discussion forums, blogs, social networking and online shopping sites.

Today's digital communication medium is a complex web of all these technologies, sometimes used as an integral communication network. Added to these already complex communication technologies the new integration of Mobile phones into this network makes it much more complex, where the telecommunication employees are always connected to share information and communicate even while on the move (Bisgwa, 2018).

Employee Performance

Understanding the performance of each employee is essential as crucial management decisions are based on individual performance (Sonntag et al., 2008), leading to organizational success. Performance is defined as behaviour that accomplishes results (Armstrong & Taylor, 2014). Individual job performance is defined as things that people do, and actions they take, that contribute to the organization's goals (Campbell & Wiernik, 2015). Moreover, performance behaviours are the total set of work-related behaviours that the organizations expect the individual to display (Griffin, 2005). Lots of researchers examined two types of individual job performance. The first one is the task performance (Kappagoda, 2012) or the inrole performance (University of Minnesota Libraries Publishing, 2015), and the other is the contextual performance (Kappagoda, 2012) or the organizational citizenship behaviours (OCBs) (University of Minnesota Libraries Publishing, 2015).

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However, some researchers identified new types of job performance that are going to be defined in the following. Robbins et al. (2013) listed three major types of behaviour that constitute performance at work. The first one is task performance which is "performing the duties and responsibilities that contribute to the production of a good or service or to administrative tasks". The second type is citizenship which is the "actions that contribute to the psychological environment of the organization, such as helping others when not required, supporting organizational objectives, and treating co-workers with respect". While counterproductivity - as negative behaviours - is the actions that actively damage the organization. These behaviours include stealing, damaging company property, and behaving aggressively toward co-workers (Robbins & Judge, 2013). **Providing Feedback on Employee Performance**

Evaluations of performance are fed back to the individual and relevant decision-makers. In a performance management system, feedback plays an important role both for motivational and informational purposes and for improved rater-ratee communications. For example, supportive feedback can lead to greater work motivation for employees and feedback discussions about pay and advancement can lead to greater employee satisfaction with performance management processes. In effect, providing people with feedback about their performance will have positive effects on their future performance (Taylor & Pierce, 1999).

Research (Bernardin et.al., 2016; Bobko & Colella, 2014; London et al, 2011; Mikkelsen et al., 2017; Pettijohn et al., 2011) demonstrated that clear, specific, and descriptive feedback, compared to evaluative outcome feedback, resulted in more accurate evaluations of expectancy for success, led to perceptions of source credibility and fairness, and increased performance by allowing for accurate attributions about past performance. However, it is often reported that feedback to inform poor performers of performance deficiencies and to encourage improvement doesn't always lead to performance improvement.

Theoretical framework

Adaptive Structuration Theory (AST)

The theoretical background is to better capture under what conditions the digitally transformed home office can improve Telecommunication employees' job well-being and job productivity. Adaptive Structuration Theory (AST) was developed by DeSanctis and Poole in 1994. This theory looks at how the technology is designed and how the technology is used and interpreted by the end user. Despite it being originally a group-level analysis theory, we argue it is also relevant for an individual level of analysis.

From This perspective, digital tools have characteristics that are constraining, that is they are not modified by the user once they are implemented. The technology choice by the user considers the 'spirit' of the technology (DeSanctis & Poole, 1994). Towards digital tools, which use remains optional, the user can adopt various behaviours: total rejection, minimal use, or intensive use. Total rejection means that the user prefers to keep IHS old way of working; the technology thus is not adopted.

The theory is relevant to this study because it explains the use and effects of digital communication for the use in organization. It also focuses on the dynamic relationship between the structure provided by digital media that is document, information sharing, and how those structures are used by the telecommunication employees. The outcomes of digital media use in employee performance are ultimately contingent upon how structures are appropriated. This shows that in complex systems, technology and organizational structures co-evolve, and users adapt technology to their needs, creating shared meaning about the role and utility of technology in various

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settings. The theory can be employed in telecommunication companies to explore how the companies produce, reproduce and transform their services and operations through social interaction across time and space.

System Theory

Von Bertalanffy is said to be the one that gave the fullest formulation of a general theory of systems. He is generally regarded as the father of the systems theory. The system theory is said to be one of the contemporary approaches to organizational communication. It sees an organization as a system (made up of subsystems) within a larger or super system (that is the larger society). The theory, therefore, focuses on issues of synergy, interdependency, and interconnections within an organization and between the organization and the dangerous environment (Laszlo & Krippner, 2013).

The system theory (like the situation theory) has been described as a theory of relationship as it gives us a way of thinking about relationships (Rakeshkr, 2011) within organizations and between organizations and their larger environment, such relationships can be initiated and managed through effective internal communication. This means that communication mechanisms must be in place for the organizational system to exchange relevant information within and with its environment. The management must monitor relationships within and outside organizations. This duty is called boundary spanning. Relating this theory to the study, system theory provides insight in understanding how these digital media platforms are interconnected and how they influence communication and information flow within the organization. It also helps us see the interconnectedness and interdependencies among the different teams, departments and stakeholders in the organization, since they were all working remotely. This theory also highlights the importance of feedback loops within a system, since continuous feedback through digital media is vital for monitoring and adjusting job performance. Through system thinking organizations' can identify and address issues relating job performance, like communication gaps, work-life balance and technological limitations.

Empirical Review

Madueke, et al., (2017) surveyed the challenges and prospects of implementing EAdministration in Nigeria: An explanatory discourse. The paper was an explanatory discourse on the prospects of implementing the Electronics Administration in Nigeria and some of the drawbacks to it. Alarming ICT illiteracy rate, epileptic power supply, high cost of purchasing computer gadgets, cyber-crime, and lack of adequate manpower were among others identified as the major challenges to e-administration in Nigeria. This paper suggested mass ICT education, the establishment of e-administration implementation committees in both federal and state ministries and parastatals, the establishment of a ministry for ICT Affairs, provision of necessary ICT infrastructures and cyber security as the panacea to the challenges confronting e-administration in Nigeria.

Itigihse and Akpaetor (2014) carried out research on digital media and information dissemination in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. This study sought to determine the extent to which electronic media (e-mail, voice-mail, picture message. and live calls) influence organizational communication in tertiary institutions in the study area. The study adopted the descriptive survey design. Four specific objectives and a research question were raised and translated into a research hypothesis for testing at a .05 level of significance. A researcher-made instrument called the Digital Media Interaction Scale (DMIS) with a reliability coefficient of .87 using Cronbach Alpha was 752 respondents representing 10% of the study population was used. They were selected using stratified and random sampling techniques where the five government-owned tertiary educational institutions in

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the study area formed strata. Data collected were analysed using percentages and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The results show that digital communication media have significant influence, and ensure more effective and transactional organizational communication at diverse degrees of intensity and reach depending on authority structure and line staff within the institutions examined.

Hult and Brystrom (2021) researched challenges to learning and leading the digital workplace. Digitalization does not only transform material constructions of workplaces and work but also social constructions for employees' interaction and learning at work. The study explored emerging challenges related to the digitalisation of workplaces aiming for an understanding of the changing prerequisites for working and competence. The findings from a small qualitative exploratory study illustrate the complexity of the development of workplaces, characterised by strong but diffuse relationships between people, technology, and work practices. The study argued that in the development of digital workplaces, a sole focus on information systems as new technology, along with training and education on their functionality is insufficient. First, the demand for new competencies in the workplace calls for understanding learning practices in everyday digital work. Second, leading the transition toward a digital workplace requires learning new leadership practices.

Martin, et al., (2022) carried out a study on digitally transformed home office impacts on job satisfaction, job stress, and job productivity: Covid-19 findings. The study investigated how the usages of collaborative and communication digital tools (groupware, workflow, instant messaging, and web conference) are related to the evolution of teleworkers' subjective wellbeing (job satisfaction, job stress) and job productivity comparing during and before the first lockdown in spring 2020. Using a sample of 438 employees working for firms located in Luxembourg, This analysis enables, first, to highlight different profiles of teleworkers regarding the evolution of usages of these tools during the lockdown compared to before and the frequency of use during. Second, the analysis highlights that these profiles are linked to the evolution of job satisfaction, job stress, and job productivity. The results showed that (1) the profile that generates an increase in job productivity is the one with a combined mastered daily or weekly use of all of the four studied digital tools but at the expense of job satisfaction. On the contrary, (2) the use of the four digital tools both before and during the lockdown, associated with an increase in the frequency of use, appears to generate too much information flow to deal with and teleworkers may suffer from information overload that increases their stress and reduces their job satisfaction and job productivity. (3) The habit of using the four tools daily before the lockdown appears to protect teleworkers from most of the adverse effects, except for an increase in their job stress. **Methodology**

The research design adopted for this study was the descriptive survey design. The population of this study consisted of the IHS Tower and ZTE Nigeria Limited workers (staff) in Lagos state. According to the telecommunication companies Administrative Officers in 2023, the total population of IHS Tower is 600 and ZTE Nigeria Limited is 185. The total population of IHS Tower and ZTE Nigeria Limited staff is 785 (Seven hundred and eighty-five). To obtain the required sample size of 785 using Krejcie and Morgan Table, the sample was 254. The sampling method used by the researcher was multi-stage sampling and the data were the copies of questionnaire. Data were analysed using the descriptive and inferential statistical analysis. In other words, contingency tables were used to present data obtained from the questionnaire using a weighted mean score (WMS). In scoring data from the four-point Likert scale questions in the instrument, responses to the items were weighted. The criterion weighted mean score (CWMS) was established at 2.50, (i.e., $4 + 3 + 2 + 1 = 10$) $\div 4 =$

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2.5. The 2.5 points was used as the criterion for a decision on the responses to each item for those items that used the fourpoint Likert scale format. Hence, any mean response which is equal to or more than 2.50 was seen as positive while any mean response less than 2.50 was considered negative.

Results and Discussions Table 1: Digital Media Tools Telecommunication Employees of IHS Tower and ZTE Nigeria Limited engage in Job Performance Media

Items	SA	A	D	SD	Total	Weighted Total (fx)	Decision
In my company, digital media tools like Google drive, browsers and servers help employees to engage in job performance	188 (752)	57 (171)	8 (16)	0 (0)	939	3.71	Agreed
Media hub and YouTube facilitate my company employees in job performance	136 (544)	106 (318)	7 (14)	4 (4)	880	3.48	Agreed
Websites and portal sites are used in my company to engage job performance	170 (680)	75 (225)	6 (12)	2 (2)	919	3.63	Agreed
Podcasts, Blogs, Webcast and Skype are used in my company to engage job performance	152 (608)	92 (276)	0 (0)	9 (9)	893	3.53	Agreed
Dropbox Evernote, HBO Go and Textplus are used to engage in job performance in my company	193 (772)	45 (135)	5 (10)	10 (10)	927	3.66	Agreed
Flipboard, Piscassa and Android market are employed in my company to engage job performance	189 (756)	58 (174)	9 (18)	4 (4)	952	3.76	Agreed
Grand Mean					918	3.63	Agreed

Table 1 shows that the digital media tools telecommunication employees of IHS Tower and ZTE Nigeria Limited engage in job performance were Google drive, browsers, servers, media hub, YouTube, Websites, portal sites, podcasts, blogs, webcast, Skype, dropbox, Evernote, HBO Go, Textplus, Picassa, Androi and Flipboard.

Table 2: How Effective Telecommunication Employees of IHS Tower and ZTE Nigeria Limited are in Job Performance Using Digital Media Media

Items	SA	A	D	SD	Total	Weighted Total (fx)	Decision
Efficiency, innovation and ability gain or keep competitive advantages in employees' job performance using digital media	198 (792)	47 (141)	4 (8)	3 (3)	944	3.73	Agreed
Facilitates problem-solving in employees' job performance using digital media	137 (548)	104 (312)	6 (12)	6 (6)	878	3.47	Agreed
Improves profit margin by increasing operational efficiency and productivity in employees' job performance using digital media	175 (700)	70 (210)	2 (4)	6 (6)	920	3.64	Agreed
Innovating solutions and increase sharing of knowledge through digital media	152 (608)	82 (246)	10 (20)	9 (9)	883	3.49	Agreed
Promotes business processes and helps employees to collaborate more easily across boundaries	198 (792)	40 (120)	5 (10)	10 (10)	932	3.68	Agreed

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Provides employees with a way to collaborate more production	149 (596)	92 (276)	8 (16)	4 (4)	892	3.53	Agreed
Grand Mean					908	3.59	Agreed

Table 2 shows that telecommunication employees of IHS Tower and ZTE Nigeria Limited were effective in using digital media be being efficiency, innovative, ability to gain or keep competitive advantages, facilitate problem-solving, improve profit margins by increasing operational efficiency and productivity, innovating solutions, increase sharing of knowledge, promotes business processes, help employees collaborate more easily across boundaries and provide employee with a way to collaborate more production. **Discussion of Findings**

The data presented in tables 1 to 2 provided the platform for this discussion which was purely done in relation to the research questions.

The result revealed that the digital media tools telecommunication employees of IHS Tower and ZTE Nigeria Limited engage in job performance were Google drive, browsers, servers, media hub, YouTube, Websites, portal sites, podcasts, blogs, webcast, Skype, dropbox, Evernote, HBO Go, Textplus, Picassa, Androi and Flipboard. This finding aligns with

Madueke, et al., (2017), who surveyed the challenges and prospects of implementing EAdministration in Nigeria: An explanatory discourse. The world is gradually moving from what it used to be a digital world. The information and communication technology wave is fast blowing across digitally every aspect of society. If properly utilized, ICT can be a veritable tool in enhancing transparency and efficient service delivery in both private and public sector administration.

The finding of this study is in congruence with the study of Itigihse and Akpaetor (2014) on digital media and information dissemination in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State,

Nigeria. The finding showed that digital communication media have significant influence, and ensure more effective and transactional organizational communication at diverse degrees of intensity and reach depending on authority structure and line staff within the institutions examined. Also, the study of Hult and Brystrom (2021) on challenges to learning and leading the digital workplace gives credence to this finding as the study pointed out that the complexity of the development of workplaces, characterised by strong but diffuse relationships between people, technology, and work practices. The development of digital workplaces, a sole focus on information systems as new technology, along with training and education on their functionality is insufficient. First, the demand for new competencies in the workplace calls for understanding learning practices in everyday digital work. Second, leading the transition toward a digital workplace requires learning new leadership practices.

The system theory that is anchored in This study gives backings to This finding, the theory elicits on how digital media such as Google drive, browsers, servers and media hubs form interconnected components within the telecommunication job performance system. It helps analyse the dynamic relationships between these tools and their impact on the overall efficiency of telecommunication employees. The theory provides a holistic perspective, allowing organizations to view the integration of digital media tools as part of a larger system. This approach helps in identifying potential synergies, dependencies and optimising the overall functioning of the telecommunication work environment.

The adaptive structural theory underpinned in this study gives backings to this finding. The theory is pertinent as it emphasises the need for organizational flexibility. In the context of telecommunication employees utilising

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digital media tools, this theory highlights the importance of adapting the organizational structure to seamlessly integrate and leverage these tools. The theory encourages organizations to evolve in response to changing circumstances. In the case of digital media tools, it allows telecommunication employees to continuously innovate and adapt their structural frameworks to optimise job performance, ensuring they remain responsive to technological advancements.

The result showed that telecommunication employees of IHS Tower and ZTE Nigeria Limited were effective in using digital media to being efficiency, innovative, ability to gain or keep competitive advantages, facilitate problem-solving, improve profit margins by increasing operational efficiency and productivity, innovating solutions, increase sharing of knowledge, promotes business processes, help employees collaborate more easily across boundaries and provide employee with a way to collaborate more production.

The finding of This study lend credence to the study of Martin, et al., (2022) on digitally transformed home office impacts on job satisfaction, job stress, and job productivity: Covid19 findings is in support of This finding as stated that the use of the four digital tools both before and during the lockdown, associated with an increase in the frequency of use, appears to generate too much information flow to deal with and teleworkers may suffer from information overload that increases their stress and reduces their job satisfaction and job productivity. The adaptive structural theory upon which this study is underpinned gives backing to this finding. The theory emphasises a flexible organizational structure, fostering an environment where telecommunication employees can innovate and explore new ways to leverage digital media effectively.

Telecommunication companies need to navigate a highly competitive landscape. Adaptive structural theory promotes organizational agility, allowing quick adjustments to strategies and operations, helping employees respond effectively to changes in the competitive landscape. The theory encourages the development of adaptive capacities within the organization, enabling telecommunication employees to respond promptly and creatively to challenges posed by the dynamic nature of digital media, this responsiveness crucial for efficient problem-solving. This theory provides a framework that enables telecommunication organizations and employees to thrive in the dynamic realm of digital media, fostering innovation, efficiency, competitive advantage and effective problem-solving.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the digital media tools employed by telecommunication employees for job performance, ranged from collaborative platforms like Goggle Drive and servers to communication tools such as chatbots and file sharing platforms. Recognising the diverse array of tools utilised underscores the importance of on-going training initiatives to maximise employees' proficiency with these technologies, ultimately enhancing their effectiveness in the telecommunication work environment.

The study underscores the effectiveness of telecommunication employees in utilising digital media to enhance efficiency, innovation, competitive advantages, problem-solving capabilities and overall profitability. The study emphasises the importance of continuous training and cultivating a culture that values innovation, collaboration and the strategic use of digital media to further elevate job performance and ensure sustained success in the everevolving landscape of the telecommunication industry.

Recommendations

Based on the result of the study, the following recommendations were made:

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1. Organizations should employ digital media tools such as Goggle drive, browsers, servers, media hubs, YouTube, websites, cloud storage, file sharing platforms, assistant gadgets, for improved job performance.
2. Telecommunication companies should encourage on-going training to optimise telecommunication employees' skills in using digital media for efficiency and innovation, fostering a culture that values continuous improvement to gain or maintain competitive problem-solving initiatives.

References

- Armstrong, M., & Taylor, S. (2014). *Armstrong's handbook of human resource management practice* (13th ed.). Michael Armstrong.
- Bernardin, H. J., Kane, J. S., Ross, S., Spina, J. D., & Johnson, D. (2016). Performance appraisal design, development, and implementation. In G. R. Ferris, Rosen, S. D., & Barnum, D. T. (Eds.), *Handbook of human resource management* (pp. 462-493). Blackwell Publishers.
- Berry, R. G. (2011). Enhancing effectiveness on digital teams: Understanding why traditional team skills are insufficient. *Journal of Business Communication*, 2(48), 186 –206. Bisgwa, T. (2018). *Decision-making under uncertainty*. St. Martins Press.
- Bobko, P., & Colella, A. (2014). Employee reactions to performance standards: A review and research propositions. *Personnel Psychology*, 47(1), 1-29.
- Campbell, J., & Wiernik, B. (2015). The modelling and assessment of work performance. *The Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behaviour*, 2, 47 - 74.
- Dessler, G. (2011). *Human Resource Management*. Tenth Edition. New Jersey: Prentice Hall Didem Pasaoglu 2013. Determining the Differences between Managers' Conceptions of Discipline. *International Journal of Business and Social Science* 4 (1), 17 -23.
- Kappagoda, S. (2012). Job satisfaction and its impact on task and contextual performance in the banking sector In Sri Lanka. 1st International Conference on Management and Economics 2012. Sahiwal: COMSATS Institute of Information Technology.
- London, M., Larsen, H. H., & Thisted, L. N. (2011). Relationships between feedback and selfdevelopment. *Group & Organization Management*, 24(1), 5-27.
- Malhotra, A., Majchrzak, A., Stamps, J., & Lipnack, J. (2015). Can absence make a team grow stronger? *Harvard Business Review*, May, 137-144
- Martins, L. L., Gilson, L. L., & Maynard, M. T. (2022). Digital teams: What do we know and where do we go from her? *Journal of Management*, 45(3), 976 – 1009.

Original Article

Mikkelsen, A., Ogaard, T., & Lovrich, N. P. (2017). Impact of an integrative performance appraisal experience on perceptions of management quality and working environment. *Review of Public Personnel Administration*, 17(3), 82-98.

Pettijohn, C. E., Pettijohn, L. S., & d'Amico, M. (2011). Characteristic of performance appraisals and their impacts on sales force satisfaction. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 12(2), 127-146.

Robbins, S. P. & Judge, T. A. (2013). *Organizational behaviour* (15th ed). Pearson Education Inc.

Sonnentag, S., Volmer, J., & Sychala, A. (2008). *Job performance*. SAGE.

University of Minnesota Libraries Publishing. (2015). *Principles of management*. Minneapolis University of Minnesota.

Zbar, J. (2012). *Teleworking & telecommuting*. Made E-Z Products Inc.